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BIODEGRADATION OF TANNINS FROM CASHEW HUSK FOR GALLIC ACID PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT:

The selection of a substrate for large – scale enzyme production by fermentation depends upon its availability and cost. In this regard the waste residue of cashew husk was used as substrate for obtaining the desired fermented product. Tannins are water soluble polyphenolic compounds found in plants as secondary metabolites which can be grouped as hydrolysable and non-hydrolysable tannins. The presence of these substances in the husk of cashew was initially extracted and their crude extract was used separately as a substrate for the production of Gallic acid through submerged fermentation by *Aspergillus oryzae*. Gallic acid production as well as the biodegradation of the substrate reached maximum within 24 to 36 h against crude tannin extract obtained from *Anacardium occidentale*. Gallic acid production was higher by almost two fold in the presence of crude tannin compared to pure tannic acid used as a substrate. It seems that the industrial production of Gallic acid, using husk extract of *Anacardium occidentale* can be a very simple and suitable alternative to presently used procedures. This method appears to be much more accurate than those reported earlier.

KEY WORDS:

Gallic acid, Tannase, Tannic acid, Trimethoprim, *Aspergillus oryzae*.

INTRODUCTION:

Some plant species have developed the ability to survive long periods of dehydration, environment with high temperature and soils poor in organic matter (1). Plants like *Anacardium occidentale* grow abundantly available in India, but have not been exploited for use or application irrespective of the fact that the husk of these plants contains high concentrations of tannins (2).

Tannins are a large class of complex phenolic compounds, comprising hydrolysable, condensed and complex tannins. Hydrolysable tannins are constituted of several organic acids, such as gallic and ellagic, which are usually linked by an ester-like bond with a glucose molecule. On acidic, basic or enzymatic hydrolysis, gallotannins produce both glucose and gallic acid. On the other hand, ellagitannins have one or more hexa-hydroxydiphenolic acid residues linked to glucose, forming a diester. Their hydrolysis results in the cleavage of glucose and hexa-hydroxydiphenolic

residues that undergo spontaneous rearrangement to lactone and finally to ellagic acid (3,4).

Gallic acid (3, 4, 5-trihydroxybenzoic acid) is used in the manufacture of trimethoprim (TMP), an antibacterial agent, in leather industry (5), and as an antioxidant (6). Ellagic acid has been reported to have antimutagenic, anticarcinogenic, antioxidant, anti-viral and anti-inflammatory activities (7–10). Several fungal strains and tannin- rich substrates have been used for the production of gallic acid (2, 5, 11). For ellagic acid, few preliminary studies have been published (12). In the present paper, the fermentation of the phenolic extracts of cashew husk to produce gallic during a solid-state fermentation (SSF) with *Aspergillus oryzae* was studied.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Plant sampling

A sample of cashew husk was collected from February to April 2009 in the A.P zone of Visakhapatnam. The collected samples were placed

in black polyethylene plastic bags, and dried in an oven at 60 °C, for a period of 7 to 10 days. After that the dried husk were powdered in a Ball mill, and stored in plastic bottles in a dark place.

Extraction of Crude Tannins

Collected cashew husk from cashew industries near to Visakhapatnam, were grained into small particles, and dried in hot air oven at 60°C for 24 hours. Tannins are extracted using water and acetone. Optimal yields are obtained from fresh tissues or freeze-dried tissues. Optimal yields are not obtained from dried tissues (tannins are irreversibly combined with other polymers). After eliminating the acetone (distillation), the pigments and lipids are removed from the aqueous solution by a solvent extraction.

Determination of moisture content

Moisture content of the sample was determined by the direct oven method of association of official Agricultural chemist (AOAC, 1960).

One gram of the Cashew husk were taken in a porcelain crucible and kept in an electric oven at 90°C for about 4 – 5 hours (until constant weight), cooled in desiccators and weighed. From the loss in the weight of the sample, moisture content was determined.

$$\% \text{ moisture content (W/W)} = \frac{\text{loss in weight}}{\text{Total weight}} \times 100$$

Extraction of Tannins

The Cashew husk were dried and milled using ball mill to get the particle size below 0.5 mm. Water is preferred as solvent in view of its high saturation limit of the dissolved solids, inherent safety and ease of separation. Tannins are extracted by using pressure autoclaving method.

The Cashew husk was collected from the Coastal area of Andhra Pradesh, India. The Cashew husk were dried and milled to get the particle size below 5mm. Small particle size achieve high extraction efficiency. Water is preferred as solvent in view of its high saturation limit of the dissolved solids, inherent safety and ease of separation. However the water used for extraction (leaching) should be soft and should not contain iron. The extraction efficiency depends on process factors like temperature, time and pressure. The material is extracted under pressure on autoclaving process at 10 PSI for 30 min and obtained extract was evaporated with vacuum filter and the obtained powder form was used for the entire experimentation. This process generally yields more extract than ordinary open vat extraction. It is generally accepted; that pressure

extraction yields a higher amount of “extract” than is obtained by the open leach method, but the product is darker in color and contains a higher proportion of non-tannin substances.

Detection of tannin by paper chromatography

Presence of tannin in the cashew husk extract was confirmed through paper chromatographic analysis. A descending mode of solvent system containing n – butanol, acetic acid and water (4:1:5) was used for the study. Detection of the spot was made by FeCl₃ (0.1 g% in 30% methanol) as coloring spray reagent (Mundal and pati, 2000) and confirmed after comparing it with standard tannic acid.

Microorganism and inoculum

Microorganism:

The non-pathogenic tannase – producing strain of *Aspergillus oryzae* obtained from the NCIM Pune, was used in the present study. They were propagated on Malt extract Agar. The spores were collected using Tween 80 (0.01 %). Czapek minimal medium was prepared using the plant extracts as the sole carbon source (pH=5.0). *Aspergillus oryzae* spores were inoculated in this medium at a concentration of 2·10⁷ spores/mL.

Culture conditions

Batches of ten Erlenmeyer flasks (250 mL) with 3 g of polyurethane foam (cubes of 0.5 cm³) sterilized and impregnated (at 70 % humidity) with 7 mL of the inoculated medium were used. Reactors were covered with brown paper and incubated at 30 °C. Kinetics of the SSF process was monitored by collecting samples at 0, 24, 48, 72 and 96 h of the process. Collected samples were washed using 25 mL of distilled water; and then the fermentation liquid was recovered by compression using a sterilized 60-mL syringe. Cotton was plugged inside the syringe to avoid the passage of particles and the collected samples were stored in small plastic bottles covered with aluminium foil at freezing temperature until further analysis.

Total tannins

Folin-Ciocalteu method (FAO/IAEA, 2000) was used for the analysis of tannins (13). In this assay, 800 mL of the sample were put into a test tube and mixed with the same volume of Folin-Ciocalteu (Sigma-Aldrich) reagent, shaken and left for 5 min. Then this solution was diluted with 5 mL of distilled water and analyzed in a UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 725 nm for the determination of total tannins and at 480 nm for hydrolysable tannins. The obtained absorbance values were analyzed against the standard curves prepared with tannic and gallic acid for total phenols and tannins, respectively.

Gallic acid

The technique reported by Sharma *et al.* (14) was used for determination of gallic acid. Citrate buffer (pH=5.0), methanolic rhodanine 0.67 % and KOH (0.5 mol/L) were needed for this assay and all reactants were pre-incubated at 30 °C for 5 min. An aliquot of 0.5 mL was mixed with 0.3 mL of methanolic rhodanine solution and incubated under the same conditions mentioned above. After that, 0.2 mL of KOH solution were added and incubated again. Finally, 4 mL of distilled water were added to the reaction mixture and incubated at 30 °C for 10 min and the absorbance was read at 520 nm.

Ellagic acid

The method proposed by Wilson and Hagerman (15) was used for the determination of ellagic acid. Inside dark test tubes 10 mg of ellagic acid or 0.1 mL of the sample were placed, and then 0.1 mL of H₂SO₄ (2 mol/L) were added. The test tubes were frozen at -15 °C for 10 min, then sealed and the air was removed with a syringe. The test tubes with ellagic acid were incubated during 24 h at 100 °C. The test tubes were washed with 3 mL of pyridine and filtered. For determination, to 1mL of filtered sample, 1.1 mL of pyridine and 0.1 mL of HCl (37 %) were added, and then the mixture was shaken and incubated at 30 °C for 5 min. After incubation, 0.1mL of NaNO₂ (0.01 %) was added and the absorbance was read at 538 nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

To evaluate antioxidant activity, the aqueous polyphenolic extracts were used as carbon source during the solid-state fermentation process using the

fungal strain of *Aspergillus oryzae*. This fungus demonstrated its capacity to degrade hydrolysable tannins and the resulting monomers were either consumed or accumulated.

Cashew husk extracts recorded the highest consumption of total phenols in the samples collected at 48 h of SSF process (Fig. 1). Initial concentration of total phenols in unfermented Cashew husk extracts was 7.29 mg/g of plant, and after 48 h of fermentation, it was 6.04 mg/g of plant.

The obtained results demonstrated that *Aspergillus oryzae* degraded the hydrolysable tannin polymers present in phenolic extract of Cashew husk. The monomers obtained by the hydrolysis of this kind of tannins were consumed by the fungus during the first 48 h of culture and then the hydrolysis products were accumulated. However, it was observed that the monomers of condensed tannins were not consumed.

The hydrolysable tannins present in the Cashew husk extracts were consumed (16 %) during the first 72 h of fermentation. At 96 h, the hydrolysable tannins were degraded and approx. 15 % of the monomers of phenolic acids were accumulated.

The biodegradation of condensed tannins and the respective accumulation of catechin monomers were proportional to time (Table 1). The fungal strain recorded a similar behavior in the fermentation kinetics of substrate tested. The highest concentration of condensed tannins was reached at 96 h of fermentation process. During the fermentation, an increase of condensed tannins of 42 % was observed.

Hydrolysable Tannins	
Time / h	Cashew husk extract $\frac{w \text{ (tannin)}}{\text{mg/g}}$
0	8.63±0.0000493
24	8.00±0.0000539
48	7.36±0.0000539
72	7.23±0.0000287
96	7.32±0.0000854
Condensed Tannins	
24	8.70±0.0001
48	9.00±0.0004
72	10.20±0.0011
96	12.40±0.0010

Table 1. Kinetic evaluation of tannins Present in aqueous phenolic extract of cashew husk.

Fig. 1. Degradation of total phenolics (TP) by *Aspergillus oryzae* in cashew husk.

The accumulation of gallic acid indicated the depolymerization of gallotannins and after its release this substance could be used as a substrate. *A. oryzae* consumed nearly 72 % of free gallic acid in the extract; the minimum concentration reported was 0.14 mg/g of cashew husk at 48 h of the process. After that, an accumulation of gallic acid was

observed, indicating that the rate of gallotannin hydrolysis was faster than the consumption rate of gallic acid. In the fermentation of cashew husk extracts, the gallotannins were depolymerised after 48 h and the glucose and gallic acid were released. The highest level of gallic acid was reached at 96 h with a value of 0.08 mg/g of cashew husk.

Fig. 2. Production of Gallic acid (GA) by *Aspergillus oryzae* phenolic extract of cashew husk

The highest consumption of total phenols and hydrolysable tannins in the phenolic extracts of cashew husk was reached at 48 h of fermentation. This could be due to the fact that the phenolic extracts of cashew husk have complex

polysaccharides, and moreover, the studied strain preferred to consume free monophenols and glycosides like gallic acid and glucose present in the extracts before the production of hydrolytic enzymes to degrade tannins.

Some tannin-rich sources and several microorganisms (2,5,11,16) have been used for gallic acid production and the hydrolytic enzyme responsible for its production is the tannase or tannin cylyhydrolase (Table 2). It had been reported earlier that tannase can also hydrolyse ellagitannins.

But the results of the present study did not show this pattern and hence we consider that this enzyme is unable to degrade ellagitannins.

Results obtained in this study are similar to those reported by Shi *et al.* (12) for valonea tannins (79.2 % at 168 h). Comparing these results, the lower rate of hydrolysis in valonea tannins could be due to low protein levels in its phenolic extracts. However, Belmares-Cerda *etal.* (17) reported better results using the same substrates as tested in this study. This could be explained by the fact that they used the cashew husk as a substrate, and this matrix has a high content of protein and tannin-protein complexes (18). Several fungal species such as *Penicillium*, *Chaetomium*, *Fusarium*, *Rhizoctonia*, *Cylindrocarpon* and *Trichoderma* (19) were reported to use the monomers of gallic acid as a substrate for the oxidative breakdown to a simple oxidative acid, which then enters the citric acid cycle (20) and is converted to pyrogallol. Finally, our results demonstrated the possibility of considering that tested cashew husk in this study, could be employed in the microbial production of antioxidants due to their high tannin content.

CONCLUSIONS:

Phenolic extracts of cashew husk can be used as a carbon source by *A. oryzae*. The gallic acid can be consumed by the fungus during the solid-state fermentation while ellagic acid is not used as a substrate. It is possible to decrease or increase the content of phenolic compounds by controlling the process of solid- -state fermentation. This study demonstrated the feasibility of the production of potent nutraceuticals. This is the first work about the use of aqueous phenolic extracts of cashew husk as a substrate for solid- -state fermentation and for the production of important nutraceuticals like gallic and ellagic acid. However, it is necessary to optimize the fermentation process.

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